
Research

Exploration of Sustainable Logistics Service Quality Evaluation Indicator System-Taking China as an Example

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Abstract: Due to the deterioration of the natural environment, the acceleration of market globalization, and the deepening of health and equity awareness, the public attaches increasing importance to sustainable development. Decarbonization and sustainability have become an inevitable trend in the development of the logistics industry. However, research on sustainable logistics service quality in academia is fragmented, and emerging market countries, including China, lack evaluation tools for sustainable logistics service quality. To fill this gap, the evaluation criteria based on environmental, economic, social, and corporate dimensions were determined by means of a literature review and experts' opinions. The results suggest that Chinese logistics service providers should focus on using environmentally friendly packaging materials, strengthening green technology innovation, and promoting the continuous optimization of logistics costs. They should also focus on employee training and rights protection, and actively fulfill their social responsibilities to build a sustainable competitive advantage in logistics services.

Keywords: Sustainable logistics service quality; Sustainable development; Evaluation indicators; Emerging economies

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Accepted: 20 February, 2024; **Published:** 29 February, 2024

How to cite this article: Sifan Zhang, Yan Jiang (2024). Exploration of Sustainable Logistics Service Quality Evaluation Indicator System-Taking China as an Example. *North American Academic Research*, 7(2), 27-32. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10727580>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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1 Introduction

The term "sustainability" was first introduced by the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) in 1987, and has gradually been adopted by most of the world's organizations, which are actively seeking to implement sustainable solutions. Along with the formulation and implementation of environmental protection laws, the advancement of market globalization, and the deepening of public health awareness, more and more logistics service providers have begun to agree with the concept of sustainability and to implement the "Triple Bottom Line" (Triple Bottom Line) development thinking in their operations. This means that companies should not only pursue profits ("economic responsibility") but also consider environmental protection ("environmental responsibility") and pay attention to the healthy and fair development of people ("social responsibility"). Based on this, foreign scholars in logistics research have in recent years put forward the concept of "sustainable logistics service quality", meaning that in the context of sustainable development, combining environmental, economic, and social aspects to improve the service quality of logistics service providers. However, most of the research on sustainable logistics service quality has focused on developed

industrialized countries, and there is a lack of in-depth discussion in developing countries and emerging markets. Moreover, the concept of sustainable logistics service quality has not been clearly defined by scholars, especially the indicators of logistics service quality dimensions related to environmental and social aspects have not been asserted. Since the implementation of sustainable practices can help organizations develop a significant competitive advantage, this paper takes China, an important emerging global economy with a large market size and rapid economic growth, as an example, and develops sustainable logistics service quality indicators in the Chinese context through literature research and expert surveys. The purpose is to provide an effective evaluation tool for Chinese enterprises to implement sustainable logistics services and improve customer satisfaction, to guide Chinese logistics service providers to better carry out sustainable business practices.

2 Literature Review

Early studies on logistics service quality were mostly based on logistics enterprises or suppliers' perspectives, the most representative being the 7Rs theory proposed by Perreault et al. in 1974 [1] and the LSQ scale proposed and created by Mentzer et al. (1999) [2]. However, given that the supply chain is not composed of a single firm, but a complex web of core firms and their upstream and downstream firms, academics are increasingly concerned about the complexity of the role of service quality on customer satisfaction and firm performance. Scholars have further focused on the industry perspective, using modeling and case studies to explore the characteristics and components of logistics service quality in different industries. Zailani et al. (2018) constructed a logistics service quality model for the halal food industry to help relevant suppliers customize their logistics services based on customer quality perceptions [3]. Jiang (2021) analyzed the domestic and international literature on logistics service quality over the past 30 years with the help of a systematic literature review method and suggested that the research on service quality of "niche" industries, such as crowdsourcing logistics, railroad logistics, and cold chain logistics, should be strengthened [4]. Along with the sustainable development goals, the development of a circular economy is getting more and more attention, especially the finite nature of resources. Researchers and logistics service providers are exploring how to provide better service quality to enhance the sustainability and competitiveness of their enterprises from a macro perspective. Therefore, in the context of sustainable development, how to incorporate the relevant indicators of economic, environmental, and social aspects into the traditional logistics service quality measurement index system has become an important topic for considering the service level of logistics service providers in the context of the new era. In 1998, the British scholar John Elkington took the lead in proposing the concept of "triple bottom line" which, from the perspective of corporate social responsibility, can be divided into economic responsibility, environmental responsibility, and social responsibility [5]. Economic responsibility is the traditional corporate responsibility, which is mainly reflected in the improvement of profit level, fulfillment of tax responsibility and dividends to shareholders and investors; environmental responsibility is the responsibility of environmental protection in production and operation; and social responsibility is the responsibility of enterprises to other stakeholders. According to the "triple bottom line" theory, enterprises must fulfill the responsibilities in the above three areas simultaneously when practicing social responsibility. Based on the "triple bottom line" thinking and the goal of sustainable development, researchers believe that logistics service providers should actively carry out sustainable practices and establish a more competitive sustainable business strategy by continuously enriching the logistics service quality indicator system.

3 Scale Development

The development of the logistics industry will have a certain negative impact on the environment, and how to reduce the impact on the environment and improve logistics performance has become the focus of researchers. Souza et al. (2022) pointed out that green logistics practices such as green transportation, green warehousing, and green packaging can significantly reduce environmental pollution, and strongly improve the quality of service of logistics service providers [6]. Froio et al. (2021) analyzed the sustainable initiatives implemented by Brazilian logistics service providers and found that measures such as optimizing transportation routes, recycling waste, and reusing packaging materials

can effectively reduce the environmental burden and improve the level and performance of corporate logistics services [7]. Ali et al. (2021) combined with Egyptian law, pointed out that the environmental aspects of logistics service quality should include vehicle maintenance systems and resource environmental elements such as auditing [8]. Therefore, environmental sustainability has become an important indicator in the selection of logistics service providers and is increasingly being emphasized by enterprises, and the implementation of green practices can enable enterprises to improve the level of service quality while reducing the damage to the environment. Although prominent ecological issues have attracted the attention of many scholars, how to reduce economic costs while achieving environmental sustainability is still an ongoing concern for researchers. Hadi et al. (2022) emphasized that the use of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, advanced robotics, and blockchain are key to improving efficiency and reducing costs in the sector and can effectively contribute to the sustainability of logistics service quality [9]. Gupta et al. (2021) stated that optimizing green service costs and logistics networks are very important capabilities for organizations to gain sustainable competitive advantage [10]. In addition, the establishment of long-term relationships between logistics companies and supply chain partners can effectively improve product quality, reduce costs, accelerate delivery, promote innovation, and enhance competitiveness, and thus contribute to the sustainable development of enterprises.

Social factors have not received enough attention as economic and environmental factors. However, some studies have shown that there is a significant positive correlation between the social sustainability of a firm's supply chain and supply chain performance and that logistics service providers who consider social factors will achieve more customer satisfaction with their services. Companies that emphasize social sustainability will put society and their customers ahead of the company's interests. This unique value proposition will help the company stand out and make it more profitable, and consumers will feel more comfortable with a socially responsible logistics company. Through the related literature, it is found that the exploration of the social sustainability of logistics service quality can be categorized into internal and external factors. Internal factors mainly include employee training, improvement of the management system (Missimer et al., 2017) [11] and so on, while external factors mainly include non-financial disclosure, philanthropy, supporting community work, complying with the law and obtaining stakeholders' satisfaction (Uttam et al., 2022) [12]. In addition, to prevent the outbreak of global pandemics, the organization's emergency logistics capabilities need to be continuously strengthened (Petrudi et al., 2021) [13]. A strong level of emergency material security will effectively enhance the service quality of service providers. However, traditional logistics service quality indicators should not be ignored. On-time delivery, information quality, staff contact quality, and other indicators are still the focus of customer attention.

Although sustainable logistics service quality has received more attention, there is no clear definition of the concept. To explore the sustainable logistics service quality of Chinese local enterprises and facilitate further research, this paper defines sustainable logistics service based on the "triple bottom line" thinking and combining the research of domestic and foreign scholars. Sustainable logistics service is a sustainable operation practice adopted by logistics service providers in response to the pressure of the deteriorating environment and the call of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to combine production and operation with environmental protection and social welfare. The aim is to provide customers with sustainable logistics services to effectively improve logistics performance and the competitive advantage of enterprises, and promote the sustainable development of society. Sustainable logistics service quality reflects the ability and level of logistics service providers to implement sustainable operation practices and provide sustainable logistics services to meet customer requirements. Previous literature has explored sustainable logistics service quality to varying degrees based on the "triple bottom line" theory, but few studies have investigated the sustainability of logistics providers' service quality by integrating environmental, economic, and social dimensions, and research in developing countries has been extremely rare. In the context of sustainable development practices, there is a great need to add sustainability factors to the traditional attributes of logistics service quality. Therefore, this study integrates the "triple bottom line" theory into the traditional logistics service quality indicators in the context of China's sustainable development and establishes a sustainable logistics service quality evaluation index system that covers the

environmental, economic, social, and corporate dimensions, to further enrich the research on sustainable logistics services in emerging economies.

First, 43 initial indicators for measuring the sustainable logistics service quality of enterprises were identified through a literature review. After that, 29 experts were invited to fill out a questionnaire to evaluate the initial indicators and give suggestions. Among the experts are 10 academic research experts focusing on logistics and supply chain management and transportation, all of whom have intermediate or higher titles and more than 10 years of work experience, and 19 experts with at least 3 years of work experience as logistics directors, supply chain managers or logistics engineers. After assessment, the experts believed that some initial indicators in the evaluation index system overlapped or crossed, and retaining them would make the measurement index system more complicated and less valuable. For this reason, based on the experts' suggestions, the relevant overlapping indicators were deleted and other necessary indicators were added, resulting in a sustainable logistics service quality evaluation indicator system for Chinese enterprises, as presented in Table 1.

Table 1 China Sustainable Logistics Service Quality Evaluation Indicator System

Dimension	Criteria	Definition
Environmental	Green Warehousing	Adopting modern technology to ensure the quantity and quality of inventory, reduce environmental pollution, and lower transportation costs.
	Clean Energy Transportation Vehicles	Using new energy vehicles to complete logistics transportation.
	Environmentally friendly packaging/transportation materials	Using recyclable materials for packaging/transportation.
	Transportation Route Optimization	Optimizing logistics routes with big data and artificial intelligence to save energy and costs.
	Packaging Sharing and Recycling Services	Sharing recyclable packaging or setting up express packaging recycling boxes in communities and other logistics outlets to promote resource recycling.
	Resource Environmental Audit	Conducting comprehensive and systematic audits and evaluations of resource use, environmental governance, and other matters by certain criteria
Economic	Continuous optimization of logistics costs	Reducing the cost of waste disposal continuously through technological means, or reducing energy consumption continuously through the use of cleaner transportation.
	Green Technological Innovation	Promoting sustainable logistics development through green technological innovation.
	Sustainable Logistics Network Optimization	Optimizing the network from the three dimensions of economy, environment and social development to achieve long-term and sustainable operation of the logistics network.
	Supplier Partner Coordination	Coordinating and integrating logistics supply chain partners and building trusting relationships to promote sustainable logistics practices.
Social	Information Disclosure	Disclosing non-financial information to stakeholders and publishing reports on economic, environmental and social performance.
	Sustainable Human Resources	Providing a healthy, safe and trustworthy environment for employees, giving opportunities for training and learning, and giving due consideration to employee welfare.
	Stakeholder Satisfaction	Maintaining regular and diversified communication with stakeholders, responding to their expectations and demands promptly,

		and safeguarding their interests and rights to their satisfaction.
	Emergency Logistics Capability	Enhancing the ability to respond to public emergencies and improving the level of emergency material protection services.
	Philanthropy	Participating in charitable activities and actively undertaking social responsibility.
Corporate	Information Quality	Ensuring the reliability, availability, and shareability of information.
	On-time Delivery	Delivering products timely and accurately.
	Personnel Contact Quality	Communicating well with customers and providing personalized service.
	Responsiveness and Flexibility	Adapting flexibly to respond quickly and effectively to changes in customer needs, situations and risks.

4 Conclusion, limitations and future scope

Global environmental pressures and the demands of economic and social sustainability make it important to explore the application of sustainable development to corporate logistics services. Logistics service providers in many emerging market countries, including China, are adopting and implementing sustainable practices to optimize the use of scarce resources and take steps towards a better global future. However, research on sustainable development in emerging economies is still in its early stages, and the current research on sustainable logistics service quality in China is even more scarce. Therefore, the study in this paper helps to fill the gap of existing research. Firstly, the indicators of sustainable logistics service quality are sorted out from a systematic literature review. Secondly, the elements of the "triple bottom line" theory of environment, economy and society are integrated into the traditional corporate service indicators, to establish a sustainable logistics service quality evaluation system suitable for enterprises in China. It provides a strong theoretical reference for China's logistics providers to improve service quality and customer satisfaction and also helps to guide China's logistics service providers to develop effective sustainable business strategies and innovative solutions. For managers committed to the practice of China's logistics industry, special attention should be paid to the sustainability indicators in this study. Companies should use more recycled packaging materials, use clean energy vehicles, and make green upgrades in warehousing. In addition, enterprises need to increase innovation and investment in emerging technologies, optimize logistics costs, and pay attention to the sustainability of human resources. At the same time, enterprises should also continue to improve their organizational capacity to respond to public emergencies, strengthen their supply chain systems, and enhance their supply chain resilience to give full play to their ability to safeguard materials in emergency situations.

However, as an exploratory study conducted for the first time in a large developing country like China, this study still has some limitations. First, future research needs to continue to explore and enrich the structural dimensions and measurement indicators of sustainable logistics service quality for enterprises in countries with emerging economies. This will help logistics service providers to better improve their service quality level and promote sustainable development of the society. Second, the evaluation indicator system constructed and developed in this study needs to be further explored and enriched. In the future, vertical segmentation based on different industries can be considered to explore the sustainable logistics service quality indicators that different industries should focus on. In addition, this study is based on the background of Chinese enterprises, and whether the evaluation index system can be well generalized to other developing countries also deserves further research. We hope that more research explorations on sustainable logistics service quality of enterprises in emerging market countries can emerge in the future.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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